

HISTORY OF RUSSIAN LANGUAGE DEVELOPMENT AND ITS IMPORTANCE IN THE WORLD

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Abstract: *This article discusses the history of the Russian language, the modern and ancient Russian (East Slavic) language, the views of linguists in its development, the role of the Russian language in the world and its teaching in schools and universities in many countries.*

Keywords: *Russian, East Slavic, Ukrainian, Belarusian, Kyiv, Indo-European languages, Baltic, educated.*

INTRODUCTION

Language is the key to all knowledge and nature. Language is a social phenomenon that has existed in all periods of human society. The main purpose (or function) of language is to serve as a means of communication. Language thinking is inextricably linked with the human mind and serves as a means of shaping and expressing our thoughts and feelings.

There are more than two thousand languages on the planet. Among them, Russian is one of the most widely spoken. This includes all the language tools used in communication between people.

We all know that Russian is one of the largest languages in the world. Modern Russian is a continuation of Old Russian (East Slavic). Slavic languages preserve both Indo-European antiquity, both in grammar and vocabulary. (True, the most conservative of the living Indo-European languages is the Baltic: Lithuanian and Latvian.) This ancient heritage makes Russian (like the rest of the Slavs) very complex, but pleasant. Old Russian was spoken by the East Slavic tribes who founded the ancient Russian nation within the Kiev state in the ninth century. This language had great similarities with the languages of other Slavic peoples. But it was already distinguished by some phonetic and lexical features. All Slavic languages (Polish, Czech, Slovak, Serbian - Croatian, Slovenian, Macedonian, Bulgarian, Ukrainian, Belarusian, Russian) have a common root - a single proto - Slavic language, which probably existed until the X-XI centuries. In the fourteenth and fifteenth centuries, as a result of the disintegration of the Kiev state on the basis of a single language of the ancient Russian nation, three independent languages emerged: Russians, Ukrainians and Belarusians, which became

national languages with the formation of nations. The formation and development of the tradition of book writing in Russia, the main stages of the history of the Russian language, the first Cyrillic texts appeared among the Eastern Slavs in the X century. In 988 he began writing books in Russian. The chronicle tells the story of many scribes who worked during the time Yaroslav don. Often liturgical books are appropriate. The originals of the East Slavic manuscripts were mainly South Slavic manuscripts of the works of Cyril and Matthews, students of the creators of the Slavic script. In the process of correspondence, the original language was adapted to East Slavic.

Moreover, in our time there is no single periodicity of the history of literary language in Russian accepted by all linguists, but all researchers in the construction of chronology take into account the socio-historical and cultural-social conditions of language development. Periodization of the history of the Russian literary language L.P. Yakubinskiy, V.V. Vinogradov, G.O. Vinokura, B.A. Larina, D.I. Gorshkova, Yu.S. Sorokin and other linguists are based on observations of the norms of the Russian literary language, its relations with the ancient literary and linguistic tradition, its relations with common literary languages and dialects, the social functions and areas of application of the Russian literary language.

Most philologists of the eighteenth and twentieth centuries proclaimed the Slavic Church as the basis of the Russian literary language and came to Russia with the adoption of Christianity. Some researchers have unequivocally developed and are developing the theory of church Slavic foundations of the Russian literary language (A.I.Sobolevsky, A.A.Shakhmatov, B.M.Lyapunov, L.V.Shcherba, N.I.Tolstoy, etc.). Thus, A.I.Sobolevsky wrote: “It is known that the Church Slavonic language was first used literally from the Slavic languages”, “After Cyril and Method, it became the literary language first of the Bulgarians, then of the Serbs and Russians”. A complete reflection and conclusion of the hypothesis on the Slavic foundations of the Russian literary language obtained in the eighteenth century is given by A.A. Shakhmatov emphasizing the example of the extraordinary complexity of the formation of the Russian literary language: “No other language in the world can be compared with the Russian language in the complex historical process it has traversed”. The scholar firmly elevates modern Russian literary language to Church Slavonic as follows: “Church Slavonic (ancient Bulgarian in origin) transplanted to the soil”. A.A.Shakhmatov not only did the ancient Bulgarian language become the written literary language of the Kiev state, but already in the tenth century it had a great influence on the oral speech of the “educated strata

of Kiev”, so much of the modern Bulgarian literary speech It was believed that they and word forms exist.

LITERATURE ANALYSIS AND METHODOLOGY

In the analysis of this article, the methods of logical, historical, coherent and objective scientific knowledge were widely used. The study analyzed the history of the development of the Russian language and its importance on a global scale. President of the Republic of Uzbekistan Sh.M.Mirziyoyev's methodological guidelines for the study of history and spiritual heritage serve as a theoretical and methodological basis for the study.

DISCUSSION AND RESULTS.

From the middle of the twentieth century, the study of the Russian language became widespread throughout the world. Currently, Russian is taught in more than 100 countries around the world. In 1967, the International Association of Teachers of Russian Language and Literature, in 1973, the Institute of Russian Language named after AS Pushkin .

Russian is one of the most widely and richly spoken languages in the world, spoken by people of different nationalities outside the main area where they are spoken, communicating not only with the mother tongues of these languages, but also with themselves.

A detailed description of synonyms of modern Russian literary language, their speech features and their use in Russian speech etiquette and culture was made by A.P.Yevgenyeva. As a result of his work, in 1975 he published a one-volume "Dictionary of synonyms. Information-manual" (author's translation). In 1997, a new explanatory dictionary of synonyms of the Russian language was created at the Russian Academy of Sciences named after V.V.Vinogradov under the leadership of Yu.D. Apresyan . This dictionary is based on the principles of holistic description of the language. The dictionary describes the semantic, pragmatic, communicative and other similarities and differences between synonyms, as well as the fact that these differences are partially neutral. In general, in addition to general dictionaries in Russian linguistics, level dictionaries have been developed for lower levels of education. Russian linguists such as D.N.Ushakov, S.Y.Kryuchkov, A.N.Tikhonov, P.A.Grushnikov, Z.A.Potikha, M.R.Lvov are dealing with these problems. Various illustrative and interesting dictionaries have been created to teach students to work with dictionaries from an early age. According to Professor M.R.Lvov, the creation of such educational dictionaries for students will help to increase the level of their independent work, providing them with quality and selected language materials. It should be noted that the author of various educational dictionaries for primary

school students is Professor M.R.Lvov. This can be attributed to the example of such educational dictionaries of the scientist as “Dictionary of synonyms and antonyms of the Russian language”, “dictionary of antonyms of the Russian language for school age”, “differentiation of words and their meanings: multi-meaning words, thematic groups of words, homonyms, synonyms, paronyms, antonyms, antonyms”, “Dictionary of antonyms of the Russian language”, “Explanatory Dictionary of antonyms of These dictionaries are compiled mainly from words that are suitable for Primary School students. For example, the “dictionary of synonyms and antonym words of the Russian language” consists of five sections, in which students of small age begin to work with synonyms, in the planned case they switch to antonym words, in which there is a synonym-antonymic relationship, in which many synonyms of the synonym series and antonym pairs are given and systematized.

CONCLUSION

Like English and some other languages used abroad as a state or official state, Russian is widely used outside of Russia. For example, it is used in various fields of international (interstate) communication. It serves as a “language of science” and serves as a means of communication between scientists from different countries, a means of coding and storing universal knowledge. According to statistics, 60-70% of the world's information is published in English and Russian. Russian is a necessary communication of world communication systems (radio, air and space communications, etc.). English, Russian and other world languages are characterized not only by the specificity of state functions (for example, lingua franca function, the mediator in the dissemination and leveling of knowledge in different countries; diplomacy, international trade, transport, tourism); are consciously selected to learn and use these languages. In other words, the topic of teaching in schools and universities in many countries, its legal recognition as a “working language” at the international level, the use of Russian by people, especially at the UN, international congresses and elsewhere, show that its prestige is significantly higher.

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